

Synthesis and crystallochemical interaction of titania and zirconia based ceramic precursors[†]

O. P. Shrivastava* and Rashmi Shrivastava

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003, India

E-mail : satishrs_sgr@sancharnet.in dr_ops11@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 10 October 2002

Titania and zirconia based ceramic material useful in 'Synroc' (synthetic rock) technology of radioactive waste management contains hollandite [Ba(Al,Ti)₂Ti₆O₁₆], zirconolite (ZrCaTi₂O₇) and perovskite (CaTiO₃). ⁹⁰Sr and ¹³⁷Cs are the most heat and β -activity generating radioactive elements present in high level nuclear waste (HLW). Sr is crystallochemically incorporated via a simple substitution for calcium in perovskite type structures while Cs is entrapped in hollandite phase of the precursor. U is chemically fixed in zirconolite phase of the precursor. To simulate the crystallochemical mechanism, all three phases has been synthesized through oxide route by heating calculated quantities of respective oxides at 1150° for 8 h. 0.02 moles of strontium, cesium and uranium were added in perovskite, hollandite and zirconolite phase respectively to obtain the simulated wasteform. The sintered phases were pelleted and reheated three times to obtain the polycrystalline and densified material. Each of the titania and zirconia based synthetic phases have been characterized by X-ray powder diffraction, scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDS). Leaching studies on the ceramic phases show that the precursor material can crystallochemically incorporate Sr, Cs and U in the ceramic matrix.

The success of nuclear technology depends to a large extent on the safe management of radioactive waste. Radioactive waste management demands ecofriendly process system so that well-being of the present and future generations is taken care of. Vitrification of high level liquid nuclear waste using silicate glasses has been a proven and industrially established method for immobilization of hazardous isotopes¹. This technology basically involves heating the waste at a higher temperature (1100–1200°) with glass-forming materials. This melting technology suffers from some problems under geohydrothermal environments. Alternatively, efforts have been directed to develop multibarrier waste forms of high chemical integrity, durability and improved mechanical strength². Ringwood reported that the titania based ceramic material can fix ~20 wt.% high level waste in its matrix³. Such waste forms have excellent integrity and are leach resistant under different geochemical conditions. They can also withstand the hydrothermal conditions of the repositories. Since then the titania based ceramic precursors have attracted attention of several workers⁴. A thermodynamically stable ceramic waste form popularly known as synroc (synthetic rock) has been developed which is multi-assemblage of polycrystalline and polyphase ceramic material containing four titanate minerals : zirconolite, hollandite, perovskite and rutile. It has been reported that such ceramic precursor incorporates into its crystal nearly

all elements present in high level waste as solid solutions^{5,6}. A hot pressed synroc is reported to have very low leachability and high mechanical strength. Radioactive cesium and strontium are two isotopes which occur along with actinides and transition metals in the high level waste. Due to very high solubility in water, cesium-137 and strontium-90 are the most difficult isotopes to be immobilized, solidified and fixed in the wasteforms which could withstand the geological and hydrothermal environment for over several hundreds of years. It is, therefore desirable to study the microstructure of the wasteforms along with crystallochemical interactions of various constituent elements with such titania based ceramic precursor. In ceramic precursors, the radioactive waste constituents are immobilized as dilute solid solutions in the crystalline lattice of their host minerals. Zirconolite and perovskite are the major hosts for long-lived actinides such as plutonium, perovskite crystallochemically fixes Sr and Na while hollandite immobilizes Cs along with K, Rb and Ba. Such waste is usually separated from spent nuclear fuel in a reprocessing operation⁷. Any use of synroc therefore, comes after the treatment of spent fuel in a reprocessing plant or in remediation of old defense waste. A specialized form of it can be used to immobilize separated plutonium.

Results and discussion

Hollandite : The synthetic hollandite [Ba(Al,Ti)₂Ti₆O₁₆]

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Table 1. X-Ray powder diffraction data of synthetic hollandite phase of ceramic precursor

<i>l</i> (obs)	<i>d</i> (obs)	<i>d</i> (cal)	<i>hkl</i>
11.97	4.76	4.76	-102
25.0	3.55	3.55	102
71.35	3.42	3.42	020
100	3.16	3.16	-121
83.5	3.13	3.15	-
18.75	2.71	2.71	022
23.43	2.50	2.50	311
4.68	2.41	2.40	113
10.48	2.37	2.37	-104
33.85	2.29	2.28	-223
21.87	2.22	2.21	302
23.95	2.18	2.19	203
8.33	2.16	2.16	212
22.34	2.11	2.11	131
7.29	1.92	1.92	132
38.02	1.85	1.85	303
10.41	1.75	1.75	-333
14.07	1.68	1.67	041
10.41	1.53	1.52	-341
14.07	1.43	1.42	-516

phase matches in intensity and position with reported JCPDS⁸ file no. 19-5. Calculations on the basis of selected

20 prominent reflections out of 73 present in the X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the hollandite show that the phase is monoclinic with cell parameters : $a = 10.2336$, $b = 6.8427$ and $c = 9.5845$ Å and $\beta = 111.76$. Table 1 shows the d (obs) and d (cal) from Lazy Pulverix software⁹. The data show good correlation between observed and calculated values. Ba(Al,Ti)₂Ti₆O₁₆ is the host for large cations such as Cs, Rb, Ba and Cr. In hollandite structure the small cations Ti⁴⁺, Ti³⁺ and Al³⁺ are octahedrally coordinated and the octahedra linked together by edge-sharing to form double strings running parallel to the *c*-axis. The double strings of octahedra in turn share corners to form a three-dimensional framework which contains tunnel parallel to the *c*-axis in which the large cations are situated. The latter are surrounded by a cage of 8 oxygen anions at the corner of a slightly distorted cube, with another 4 neighbouring oxygen atoms positioned at a greater distance. The cage-like environment prevents the free migration of large cations like Ba²⁺ and Cs⁺ along the tunnel, thereby accounting for the excellent resistance of synroc hollandite to leaching by ground-water¹⁰⁻¹².

Zirconolite : The digital X-ray data consist of 5000 points between $2\theta = 3$ to 90° . The characteristic maxima is obtained at 2.93 Å. Most of the peaks match in intensity and position with the JCPDS¹³ file no. 20-1. Out of these, 25 intense peaks were selected for indexing and calculation of unit cell parameters using TREOR 90 software. The system

Fig. 1. Profile fitting diffractogram of synthetic zirconolite phase.

is monoclinic with $a = 8.51$, $b = 5.55$ and $c = 8.08$ Å and $\beta = 97.71$. Profile fitting of the phase has been done by using WINPLOTR program (Fig. 1). Zirconolite is largely responsible for the immobilization of uranium, tetravalent actinides and to a lesser degree for the immobilization of rare earths and trivalent actinides^{14,15}. Zirconolite possess an anion deficient 'fluorite' related superstructure with a monoclinic unit cell. Ca is coordinated by 8 oxygen ions positioned at the corner of a cube while Zr is in seven-fold coordination to oxygen at seven of the eight vertices of a distorted cube. Ti occupies three distinct lattice sites. In the Ti(1) and Ti(3) positions it is octahedrally coordinated to 6 oxygen ions and these TiO_6 octahedra are corner-linked forming six- or three-membered rings, respectively. The Ti(2) site is surrounded by 5 oxygen ions at the corners of a trigonal bipyramid^{16–18}. This is actually a pair of closely positioned sites, only one is being randomly occupied by Ti^{4+} .

Perovskite : The digital X-ray data consist of 2500 points between $2\theta = 5$ to 90° , where characteristic maxima is obtained at $2\theta = 33.12^\circ$. Most of the peaks matches in intensity and position with the JCPDS file¹⁹. All data points have been plotted using WINPLOTR program. Out of these, the 25 intense peaks were selected for indexing and calculations of unit cell parameters using TREOR 90 software. The values are $a = 7.65$, $b = 5.42$ and $c = 5.38$ Å. The perovskite phase with such reversed unit cell parameters ($a > b$) occurs due to change in composition on Sr addition or intensive parameters close to transition²⁰. The perovskite stoichiometry is expressed as ABO_3 where the size of the 'A' cation (divalent) is substantially large to form a closed packed array with oxygen anions while the 'B' (tetravalent) ions must fit within the octahedral holes of the A-B close packed array. The ideal perovskite structure is cubic with $a = 3.8$ Å. The structure consist of B-site cations that are octahedrally coordinated by atoms of oxygen. Larger A-site cations are surrounded by twelve atoms of oxygen in cubo-octahedral coordination within this framework. The reduction in symmetry from cubic to orthorhombic results from the presence in the A-site of cations that are smaller than required to maintain the ideal geometry of this site²¹. The calcium strontium titanate phase $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{TiO}_3$ present in nuclear waste form has orthorhombic symmetry²² and the material crystallizes in the space group of $Pnma$, the non-standard setting of space group (#62). Rietveld Analysis of the phase show the $R = 9.7\%$ and $R_p = 7.25\%$ (Fig. 2). The Ca-O and Ti-O bond distances also match the theoretical values 3.20 and 1.93 Å, respectively. Further refinement of structure is in progress. The X-ray diffractogram pattern of composite ceramic precursor shows the presence of

Fig. 2. Rietveld refinement of $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{TiO}_3$. The crosses are the raw X-ray diffraction pattern and the overlapping continuous line is calculated pattern. Vertical lines above the profile indicate the position of the allowed reflections for $\text{CuK}\alpha$. The curve at the bottom is the difference between observed and calculated intensities in the same scale. $wR_p = 9.7\%$, $R_p = 7.25\%$; Ca-O = 3.20 Å; Ti-O = 1.93 Å.

hollandite, zirconolite and perovskite phases²³. The diffraction pattern and EDS analysis of post-leached samples shows that the composite phases retain their structural integrity after 370 days of static leaching at room temperature.

²⁷Al MASNMR :

The ²⁷Al magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance (MASNMR) technique was used to determine the environment of aluminum. Aluminum is incorporated in the hollandite phase and acts as a charge compensator for aliovalent substitution of rare earth fission products and trivalent actinides in perovskite and zirconolite²⁴. It is present in relatively small quantities (~3 wt.% as oxide) and does not coherently scatter X-rays or neutrons strongly, so it has been difficult to study by diffraction methods. However, solid state high resolution Al nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy using the technique of Magic Angle Spinning has become a major technique in the study of aluminosilicate and other minerals and also in wide range of other systems including glasses, gels, fibers and catalysts^{25–29}. Hundreds of structural studies involving ²⁷Al MASNMR have been reported in recent years. ²⁷Al has 100% isotopic abundance and is easy to observe. The peak positions for Al in different coordination are well separated. Tetrahedral Al is coordinated at 50 ± 20 ppm and octahedral Al at 0 ± 10 , while five-coordinated Al appears in the 2–40 ppm range. Fig. 3 shows the major ²⁷Al peak at 8.90 and –10.72 ppm for 2 wt.% Cs-loaded hollandite phase heated at 1150°, indicating the presence of

Fig. 3. ^{27}Al MASNMR of hollandite phase of precursor.

octahedral Al environment. The splitting of the peaks shows that Al is octahedrally coordinated in two different environment. The peak at -10.72 ppm can be assigned to barium hollandite²⁴ while that at 8.90 ppm may be attributed to Al_2TiO_5 .

Scanning electron microscopy :

By scanning an electron probe across a specimen, high resolution images of the specimen with very high magnifications can be obtained. Compositional analysis of a material may also be obtained by monitoring secondary X-rays produced by the electron-specimen interaction. Thus detailed maps of elemental distribution can be produced from multi-phase materials. Characterization of fine particulate matter in terms of size, shape, and distribution as well as statistical analyses of these parameters may be performed. The scanning electron microscopy combined with energy dispersive analysis used in the study of ceramics is generally of morphological interest. The EDS data reveal that the Cs and Sr get crystallochemically fixed in the ceramic matrix. The energy dispersive analysis was also performed on a disc of the composite ceramic material which was subjected to 370 days leaching in water at 25° (Fig. 4). The atomic % of Cs and Sr has been found to be 0.24 and 3.19, respectively

Fig. 4. Energy dispersive analysis of cold pressed 370 days leached synroc precursor.

in the post-leached samples of the composite precursors. The simulated ceramic waste form specimen consists of fine grained crystals of size $0.05\text{--}1.5\ \mu\text{m}$. The size of a single crystal of synthetic perovskite is around $4.5 \times 1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ with fine particles adhering to it (Fig. 5). Well defined crystals of

Fig. 5. SEM of synthetic perovskite phase of ceramic precursor in single crystal.

cesium hollandite may be seen in Fig. 6. Similar morphology and crystal size have been reported elsewhere³⁰.

Leach rate study :

The leach rate is defined as : $l.w/c.t.s$, where l is the quantity of ion leached in solution ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), c the quantity of ion left in solid disc ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), w the wt. of the disc (g), t the leach time (days) and s the surface area of the disc (cm^2). The leach rate study of Cs and Sr on cesium and strontium loaded hollandite and perovskite phase, respectively, was

Fig. 6. SEM of synthetic hollandite phase of ceramic precursor in single crystal.

carried out at 25°. The leach rate of Sr and Cs is expressed as cumulative percent of cesium and strontium released in water against time in days. There are two types of mechanism³¹ which may effect the integrity of simulated solid waste form, the first is the leaching mechanism which may selectively extract a particular species by the ion exchange leading to predominance of these species released into solution and corresponding concentration profile in the

Fig. 7. Plots of cumulative % of Cs and Sr leached against leaching time.

solid interface layers which are depleted; the second one is a dissolution mechanism which may affect whole surface layers leading to release of some or all species into solution in combination with formation of precipitate phase depending upon the solubility constraints. At 25°, the extent of attack and release of Ca^{2+} into solution is limited by the formation of a titanous amorphous layer which imposes a reaction constraint at the film solid interface³². The leaching data show that 86% of Sr^{2+} remains fixed in the matrix after 90 days of static leaching at 25°. The leach rate data on the simulated ceramic wastefoms have been summarized in Fig. 7.

Experimental

Three well known methods were reported for synthesis of ceramic precursors : oxide route, alkoxide route and sol-gel method. The materials in the title study were synthesized by sintering the calculated quantities of starting materials at 1150° for 8–10 h. Each preparation was repelletized and sintered three times under similar conditions. The hollandite phase was synthesized by sintering calculated quantities of barium, titanium and aluminum at 1150°. Ba was taken as BaCO_3 , Al as Al_2O_3 and Ti as TiO_2 . Zirconolite was prepared by oxide route method. Ca was taken as CaO , Zr as $\text{Zr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, and Ti as TiO_2 and U as uranyl nitrate. The dry mixture was heated in muffle furnace at 1400° for 3 h. The product changed from white to light yellow due to addition of uranium. The starting materials for fabrication of the perovskite phase were equimolar quantities of calcium and titanium oxides along with calculated quantity of strontium ($x = 0.02\text{--}0.2$) as strontium nitrates $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. All chemicals were thoroughly mixed in mortar pestle and kept for heating in a muffle furnace for 8 h at 1150° with intermediate grindings and pelletization. X-ray data were collected on D Bruker axe D8 Advance diffractometer. The ^{27}Al NMR studies were carried out on a Bruker Advance DSX 300 spectrometer. SEM along with EDS were performed on a Joel JSM 5600 instrument. The chemical analysis of Cs and Sr were performed on a GBC 902 atomic absorption spectrophotometer at 852.1 and 460.7 nm, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. T. N. Guru Row, Prof. A. K. Ganguly and Dr. J. P. Shrivastava for X-ray diffraction data and to Director, R.R.L., Bhopal, for scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive spectroscopic analysis. Thanks are due to Director, I.I.Sc., Bangalore, for ^{27}Al NMR studies. The authors also thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Research Associateship to one of them (R.S.).

References

1. "International Atomic Energy Agency, Technique for the Solidification of High Level Waste", Technical Report Series No. 176, IAEA, Vienna, 1997; "International Atomic Energy Agency, Design and Operation of High Level Waste Vitrification and Storage Facility", Technical Report Series No. 339, IAEA, Vienna, 1992.
2. K. Balu, *Indian Assoc. Nucl. Chem. Allied Sci. Bull., BARC*, 1997, **11**, 3.
3. A. E. Ringwood, "Safe Disposal of High Level Nuclear Reactor Waste: A New Strategy", Australian National University Press, Canberra, 1978.
4. V. N. Zyryanov and E. R. Vance, 'Mater. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc. (Scientific Basis for Nuclear Waste Management XX)', 1997, 409; R. Giere, C. T. Williams and G. R. Lumpkin in "Scientific Basis for Nuclear Waste Management Symposium", eds. I. G. Mckinley and C. McCombie, Mater. Res. Soc., Warrendale, 1998; M. W. A. Stewart, M. L. Carter, S. Moricca, D. S. Perra and E. R. Vance, *J. Aust. Ceram. Soc.*, 1997, **1**, 43.
5. K. D. Reeves and A. E. Ringwood, 'The Synroc Process for Immobilization of High Level Nuclear Waste', presented at 'IAEA International Conference on Radioactive Waste Management', IAEA-CN-43/127, Seattle 1983, 16-20; S. Myra, A. Atkinson and J. C. Riviere, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1984, **67**, 223; A. E. Ringwood, *Min. Mag.*, 1985, **49**, 159.
6. A. E. Ringwood, V. M. Oversby, S. E. Kesson, W. Sinclair, N. Ware, W. Hibberson and A. Major, *Nucl. Chem. Waste Management*, 1981, **2**, 287.
7. H. Mitamura, T. Murakami, T. Banaba and T. Amaya, *Nucl. Tech.*, 1986, **73**, 384.
8. Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards 1989 Card No. 19-5, Newton Square, Pennsylvania, USA.
9. K. Yvon, W. Jeitschko and E. Parthe, Lazy Pulverix, Laboratoire De Crystallographie Aux Rayons-X, Universite De Geneve, Geneva, Switzerland.
10. W. Sinclair, G. M. McLaughlin and A. E. Ringwood, *Acta Crystallogr. (B)*, 1981, **36**, 2913.
11. L. A. Bursill and G. Grzinic, *Acta Crystallogr. (B)*, 1980, **36**, 2903.
12. W. Sinclair and R. A. Eggelton, *Am. Mineral.*, 1982, **67**, 615.
13. Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards 1989 Card No. 20-1, Newton Square, Pennsylvania, USA.
14. S. E. Kesson, W. Sinclair and A. E. Ringwood, *Nucl. Chem. Waste Manage.*, 1983, **4**, 259.
15. F. W. Clinard, Jr., L. W. Hobbs, C. C. Land, D. E. Peterson, D. L. Rohr and R. B. Roof, *J. Nucl. Mater.*, 1982, **105**, 248.
16. H. J. Rossel, *Nature*, 1980, **283**, 282.
17. F. Mazzi and R. Munno, *Am. Mineral.*, 1983, **68**, 262.
18. B. M. Gatehouse, I. E. Grey, R. J. Hill and H. J. Rossell, *Acta Crystallogr. (B)*, 1981, **37**, 306.
19. Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards 1989 Card No. 8-91, Pennsylvania, USA.
20. A. Yoshikawa, A. Saitow, H. Horiuchi, T. Shishido and T. Fukuda, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 1998, **266**, 104.
21. H. R. Mitchell, C. P. Burns and Chakhmouradian, *Can. Mineral.*, 1998, **38**, 145.
22. H. F. Kay and P. C. Bailey, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1957, **10**, 219.
23. O. P. Shrivastava and R. Shrivastava, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 407.
24. J. S. Harthman and E. R. Vance, *J. Mater. Res.*, 1994, **9**, 1714.
25. C. A. Fyfe, "Solid State NMR for Chemists", C.F.C. Press, Ontario, 1983.
26. G. Engelhardt and D. Michel, "High Resolution Solid State NMR of Silicates and Zeolites", Wiley, New York, 1987.
27. R. J. Kirkpatrick *Rev. Mineral.*, 1988, **18**, 213.
28. R. J. Kirkpatrick and B. L. Phillips, *Appl. Magn. Reson.*, 1993, **4**, 213.
29. M. E. Simth, *Appl. Magn. Reson.*, 1993, **4**, 1.
30. J. I. Goldstien, D. E. Nerburg, P. Echling, D. C. Joy, C. Fion and E. Lifshen, "Scanning Electron Microscopy and X-Ray Microanalysis", 1981, 76.
31. S. Myrha, St. C. Smart and P. S. Turner, *Scanning Microsc.*, 1988, **2**, 715; "Nuclear Waste Materials Handbook Test Methods", Material Characterization Centre, Pacific Northwest Laboratory DOE/TIC-1400 Rev. 1, 1983.
32. D. K. Pam, F. B. Negall, S. Myrha, R. St. C. Smart and P. S. Turner, *Mat. Res. Soc. Sym. Proc.*, 1990, **176**, 249.